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THE INNOVATIVE METHOD OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: The essence of the content of this article is as followed, today, the ability to know foreign languages are becoming one of the intotal parts of higher education. In order to improve the quality of educating English language of teachers are utilizing new innovative methods. Helps schoolchildren to quickly remember English words, to write down the words without mistakes, to learn methods of correct pronunciation. This article explores some of the most beneficial and successful innovative methods being adapted by educators and teachers.

Keywords: innovative methods, interesting games, express-methods, professional education, pedagogical technologies, English language, psychological characteristics.

Introduction. English is one of the foreign languages that creates necessary opportunities to bring the beautiful image of Uzbekistan to the international arena. Among foreign languages, English is the most spoken language, it is the 3rd most spoken language in the world, and it is the main language of European Union. According to statistics, the native speakers of English language compromises of 2 billion people. English is an official language of the United Nations, the language of business, the media, the online world and the language of many academics.

Literature review and methodology. These days, the required for learning English in Uzbekistan is increasing day by day. According to the decision of the President of Uzbekistan, adopted on December 10, from the 2013, teaching the English language to school pupils will begin from the 1st grade. Scholars from the United States and England provide support to the Ministry of Education in the development of methods and programs for teaching English in Uzbekistan and in the creation of manuals. For instance, the USA has established a "Regional English Language Office" for the countries of Central Asia. The office regularly organizes a great deal of trainings and seminars to advance the skills of English language teachers in the region. Also, the "British Council" office of England which is situated in

Tashkent, has introduced special programs for students and teachers. Sanobar Khojanazarova says that these organizations are helping us to ensure the implementation of the new decision. Teacher should not be limited only to the textbooks. One ought to create ones own educational materials and innovative methods according to the program.

It is becoming a tradition to teach lessons through interactive games in schools. N. A. Balakina (2016) says that the lesson is conducted on the basis of a great deal of games, which allows pupils to show off their abilities, concentrate, increase their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. Educational materials an innovative methods help to learn the language easily. Playing a great deal of games during the lesson increases the enthusiasm for learning science in the classroom, encourages the passive children to participate better in the lessons, and creates an environment of competition and groupwork among the schoolchildren in the classroom. It also increases pupils respect for their teachers. Below you will find games that help to further increase the effectiveness of teaching during English lessons.

Primary school pupils can learn English quickly with intersting and innovative methods. Let's focus on these educational materials and interesting, innovative methods:

1. Singing the English alphabet is a more effective way for learning English alphabet than just memorizing.
2. When learning English, even if the students do not understand the words of the cartoon characters, they try to understand through the actions.
3. Remembering words through role playing. For instance, One pupils will point out the sound or movement of an animal, and the others will guess, "What animal is this?".
4. A method of remembering through gestures.
5. Efimenko (2016) the pupils remember the subject faster. If they always see pictures. Therefore, It is a good way to use visual aids related to the topics. For instance, animals, birds, colors, fruits and others.
6. The teacher should create that environment based on the topic. For instance, travelling, museum , in the kitchen , birthday. Organization a trip by the teacher on the topic of travel. They get information about what kinds of transport can be used and where to travel. This helps to strengthen the student's language abilities, increase vocabulary, and change his worldview.
7. Most speakers are familiar with Pictionary. Mineeva (2016) use this, For the purpose of drawing, you can utilize regular blackboard for each group. You will write down the grades of the groups here. One person from team A comes out. And chooses one of some upside down words and draws that word on the board. And others will have to find out it. The team that guesses the word first gets correctly and quickly a point. The team with 5 points is the winner.
8. Charades is similar to Pictionary, However, the main difference is that it utilizes actions rather than pictures to represent words. This game comes in handy when your schoolchildren are bored and sleepy. Get them up and moving! Write some words on several square cut papers for students to choose from. Verbs are much easier to express. But you can utilize words that are a little more complicated, but that all pupils know.

Divide the class into two groups. And one student from each group chooses a piece of paper with a word written on it and expresses it with an action. Team members will have to find that word within 2 minutes. For each correct answer, one point is given. The team with 5 points is the winner.

Methods for high school pupils:

1. Listening and sing a song in English, write down words and memorizing which you do not know.

Taboo words

2. Taboo words help school children practice word charts and synonyms. The class is divided into two teams and the groups sit facing each other. Each team chooses one pupil from their team to sit in the chair opposite them. The teacher goes behind the students and holds a word written on a large piece of paper. Students sitting in their seats should not be able to see this word. The team member sitting in the seat will have 2 minutes to say the word you are holding. The main thing is that they should not use this word at all. Advice for playing in large classes. If you have more than 10 students in your class, it can be a bit noisy and chaotic during the game. This case, you can divide everyone into small groups of 5 who participate only when it's their. Using this game by Sofowora (2011)

Objects

3. Test your students memory and vocabulary with this game at the time. All you need is a whiteboard and 20 classroom supplies. You can even use your own bag or carry-on items. Place all the items on the table and ask your students to call them all and look at them. Then cover all the items after a minute with paper. Ask all of your students to go back to their seat and write down in English what they remember on a piece of paper. When everyone has finished, write the list of items on the board and ask students to check themselves. You can ask them to read the words one by one and mark the correct ones.

Real –time polling

4. Real-time polling – Teachers can utilize a live polling tool to pulse pupils. Of course, they can ask students on video to raise their hands or click a hand raise button, but even better is a polling tool to gauge measurable feedback. With preset polling options, teachers can launch a poll with a click. Then students select their reply and teachers see real time aggregate results as well as what each student replied.

Interact whiteboards and file annotations

5. Interactive whiteboards and file annotations -want students actively participating in their learning. What better way to encourage that than with an interactive whiteboard. A whiteboard is a great space for students to share their ideas, collaborate, and brainstorm

Last Man Standing

6. Last Man Standing .This game is a quick game. But it gives readers some time to think. This is a game encourages collaborative learning, that is, while other students are speaking, the rest of the students are thinking of words themselves. You need a ball to play the game. And all students should stand in a circle. You will need to choose a topic. For example: Things found in a kitchen, food, profession, etc. The game starts by throwing the ball to a student. That student says an English word about the topic and throws the ball to the next student. Each student who receives the ball will have to say something about this topic. If they repeat the spoken words or cannot find the words within a few seconds, they leave the game and watch the game while sitting. Don't worry, they will still be learning.

Prepare an image

7. Prepare an image with random objects placed on a table or in a room. Show the image for a certain time - 20-60 seconds to remember what is in the image. During this time, they are not allowed to

screenshot, take pictures or write objects. Remove the picture and ask students to list what they remember. Using this method by Egbowon (2005).

Today, we live in the age of information technology. This has brought enough changes to education. The Conditions created by our state in the schools, they are equipped with modern equipment, they are provided with young and educated personnel, the organization of online courses after school lessons are commendable. Teachers should also work on themselves while teaching students, make lessons interesting, use colorful visual aids, use interesting games related to the topic so that students do not get bored during the lesson, listed above all opportunities have been created to use innovative methods, to attract inactive students to the lesson, to use online lessons, movies, music, audio books on the subject to learn the language more easily. The teacher should divide into 3 types according to the student's receptive capacity. It is necessary to separate the fast adopters into one group, the average adopters into one group, and the slow adopters into one group. The use of correct and innovative methods will help the student to learn quickly and easily.

Conclusion. To conclude the article, the use of interesting and innovative methods based on modern technologies by teachers of general education schools, taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students, increases the student's interest and potential in the English language, and helps to learn quickly and easily.

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